

Supplementary material to the paper:

E. S. Medvedev, V. G. Ushakov, Irregular semi-empirical dipole-moment function for carbon monoxide and line lists for all its isotopologues verified for extremely high overtone transitions.

Line lists contain the following columns:

v', J', v'', J'' ,	quantum numbers of the upper and lower states, respectively;
$m = 0.5[J'(J'+1) - J''(J''+1)]$,	line index;
E'' ,	energy of the lower state in cm^{-1} ;
ν ,	transition wave number in cm^{-1} ;
TDM,	transition dipole moment in debye;
A,	Einstein A coefficient in s^{-1} ;
S,	line intensity in $\text{cm}/\text{molecule}$ calculated at 296 K and 100% abundance.